

Sorption of aqueous fluoride by active silica-carbon from rice husk

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Abstract : Fluoride in drinking water in excess of desirable levels has been a serious threat to public health in many places in India. Distilled water containing 5 ppm fluoride (dissolved as NaF) passed through a glass column (2.5 cm id) packed with 10 g of iron-impregnated active silica-carbon composite char derived from rice husk, yielded treated water with fluoride concentrations between 1 and 2.5 ppm, that are desirable as per drinking water standards in India and elsewhere.

Keywords : Drinking water standards, fluorides, rice-husk, silica-carbon composite char.

Introduction

Fluoride in low concentrations in drinking water is considered beneficial for dental health in humans and excessive fluoride has been linked to chronic fluorosis leading to disabilities, deformities and even death¹. In India the specified desirable level of fluoride in drinking water is 1.0–1.5 ppm².

But in many localities all over India drinking water containing excessive fluoride (>5 ppm, sometimes ~20 ppm) has posed a serious public health problem^{3,4}. Until now there is hardly any remedy.

Rice husk (RH) is a unique biomass. It contains 15–20% of silica on dry weight basis⁵. The entire silica or part of it may be retained as a composite with carbon in an active and amorphous state in processes broadly described as *carbonization*. Carbonaceous materials derived from RH containing all or part of the silica described conventionally as active carbon⁶, should preferably be called active *silicarbon* (SC).

It is possible to prepare *active silicarbon* from RH, unmodified or modified by metal impregnation or chemical treatment. Such *active silicarbon* materials derived from RH possess immense potential in treatment of industrial wastewater, in decontamination of drinking water and in combating hazardous gaseous pollutants^{7–11}. Defluoridation of drinking water¹² and removal and immobilization of arsenic^{13,14} on RH have also been reported.

This article elucidates the usefulness of iron-impregnated active silicarbon (SC-Fe) materials derived from RH in reducing excess fluoride burden to acceptable limits in drinking water.

Results and discussion

Silicarbons from RH :

Identification and properties (bulk density, pH of 1% suspension, BET surface area and ash content) of silica-carbon materials derived from RH and those of a few other sorbents tested for gaining comparative ideas are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 depict the Scanning Electron Microscopic images (back scattered) of RH and its Fe-impregnated carbonized (silicarbon) product. It is apparent from Fig. 2 that the carbonized material preserves, by and large, the cellular nature of RH and is highly porous. Fig. 3 (a, b and c) show the FTIR spectra of silicarbon material derived from un-impregnated RH (SC-U), those derived from iron impregnated RH (SC-Fe) and silica gel in the wavelength range 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹. Both SC-U and SC-Fe exhibit the usual stretching bands due to O–H (3740–3420 cm⁻¹), bending vibration attributable to C–O (2280–2214 cm⁻¹) and a strong band (1090–1055 cm⁻¹) representing the internal asymmetric stretching of SiO₄ skeleton. Overall, spectra for both samples resemble those of amorphous fused silica¹⁵ and of silica gel (Fig. 3c).

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Table 1. Some characteristic properties of sorbents tested

Sorbent ID	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	pH of 1% suspension	BET surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	Ash content (% of dry solid)	Fluoride pick-up (mg g ⁻¹)
RH (Raw dry RH)	0.15	7.8	40	19.6	0.24
SC-U (Silica-carbon composite from RH-untreated)	0.11	8.5	95	51.2	0.31
SC-Fe (Silica-carbon composite from RH-Fe treated)	0.13	8.7	155	48.8	0.42
C (RH) (Carbon from RH silica leached out)	0.10	8.8	97	4.9	0.26
C (comm) (Commercial carbon from coconut shell)	0.17	7.5	140	10.0	0.27

The signal due to stretching of SiO₄ skeleton loses its intensity in SC-Fe (Fig. 3b) due to gaining in symmetry in the skeleton. Thus Fe impregnation brings about modification of the silica-carbon composite products derived from RH.

Fluoride sorption capacity of silicarbons and other sorbents :

Fig. 4 shows the concentration of residual fluoride in solutions treated with SC-Fe in batch tests as a function of time of treatment. Each point in the figure represents an average concentration of three measurements. Fig. 4 indicates that the fluoride concentration is quickly reduced from 5 ppm to ~2.5 ppm in 5–10 min and maintains a steady concentration between 1.5–2.5 ppm up to ~1200 min.

In the batch experiments with different sorbents identified in Table 1, the duration of treatment was selected at 20 min as preliminary experiments showed this duration to be sufficient to reach a steady value. The average sorption capacities (five tests for each) expressed as mg (F⁻) per g of sorbent, calculated from actual experimental information are included in Table 1.

It is seen from the table that all the five sorbents tested possess capacities to pick-up fluoride, but the iron-impregnated silica-carbon composite material derived from RH (SC-Fe) is by far the best followed by the carbonized material from non-impregnated RH (SC-U). RH itself has significant capacity close to that of silica-free carbon de-

rived from SC-U and of commercial carbon (from coconut shell). It is observed (Table 1) that silicarbon prod-

Fig. 1. SEM of Rice Husk (lemma/palea).

Fig. 2. SEM of Fe impregnated *silicarbon* from RH (base area).

Fig. 3(a). FTIR absorption bands of SC-U

Fig. 3(b). FTIR absorption bands of SC-Fe.

Fig. 3(c). FTIR absorption bands of silica gel.

ucts, impregnated or non-impregnated, are definitely better than silica-free carbon or raw RH or commercial active carbon. This suggests that silica present integrally in the SC products and the impregnated metal (Fe) both have positive role in the fluoride sorption capacity of SC products.

Fluoride pick-up by iron-impregnated silicarbon in a packed column :

The results of this experiment are presented in Fig. 5 that shows the fluoride concentration in the effluent against the cumulative volume of F⁻ solution passed through the column at a constant rate, ~25 ml min⁻¹, for a total volume of 113 litres. It is observed that fluoride concentration quickly goes down from 5.0 ppm to < 2.5 ppm

Fig. 4. Sorption of fluoride by SC-Fe with time of contact (batch test).

and maintains the concentration in the range 1.0–2.5 ppm right up to ~110 litres of solution passed. Thus active silicarbon materials derived from RH can be effective in removing fluoride from drinking water containing excessive fluorides.

Fig. 5. Concentration of fluoride with cumulative volume of treated water in continuous flow column (packed bed of SC-Fe).

The trend line (second order) of the plot in Fig. 5, however, indicates that the break time (t_b = time of beginning of contaminant/solute to break through the bed) was crossed but the saturation time (t_s = time required for the effluent to come to the same concentration as that of the influent liquid) was not reached. The break volume was found out from the point of intersections of tangents at the points of beginning and of the end of the trend line, the saturation volume could be estimated from the extrapolation of the trend line up to $y = 5$. The rate of flow remaining constant at 25 ml min⁻¹, t_b and t_s could be calculated at 2384 min and 6384 min respectively. The mass transfer zone (MTZ) as applicable to dynamic column studies¹⁶ could thus be calculated

$$MTZ = L (t_s - t_b) / t_s = 15 (0.64) \text{ cm} = 9.6 \text{ cm}$$

Since the sorbent bed volume is 100 ml and the flow rate is 25 ml/min the residence time is 4 min and is shorter than what could be considered optimum (*cf.* Fig. 3). These information and parameters are useful for development of practical gadgets like a domestic water filter system.

It is presumed that a longer bed length covering at least two MTZ's and bottom-feeding of solution (upflow) would result in a longer residence time at similar flow rates and would yield better results in terms of available total volume of treated water and in terms of smaller fluctuations in the concentrations of fluoride in the treated water (*cf.* Fig. 5).

Subsequent washing of the column with fluoride-free water passed at rates of 20–40 ml min⁻¹ resulted in effluents with F⁻ concentrations in the range of 0.2–0.4 ppm, indicating that the F⁻ held by the sorbent bed is not easily leached out.

Conclusions :

Controlled carbonization of rice husk at ~800 °C yields products containing silica and carbon in approximately 1 : 1 ratio by (wt) and are non-crystalline and active. They may be obtained in metal-impregnated forms. An iron-impregnated silicarbon is efficiently active in sorbing out fluorides in excess of limits desirable for drinking water. Domestic water filter systems can be developed with columns packed with silicarbon materials to reduce the toxic fluoride burden of drinking water contaminated with fluorides beyond acceptable limits.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Preparation of active silicarbon and their characterization :

Described in a recent communication¹⁷, the method essentially involves heating RH or RH pre-impregnated with a metal salt in a closed mild steel reactor fitted with outlet for volatiles and gases to be released or collected, at controlled rates up to a temperature of ~800 °C. In the present case, iron impregnation to the extent of 2% as Fe on the basis of dry weight of RH, was achieved by spraying with a solution of ferrous sulfate (FeSO₄·7H₂O).

The contents of the reactor were collected after cooling, weighed and preserved in airtight containers for subsequent tests. Silicarbon materials thus derived maintained the overall shape of RH and were used as such in the tests as a soft granular form of sorbent.

The silicarbons and other sorbents used for comparison were characterized by measurement of their bulk den-

sity (BD), pH of 1% suspension, BET surface area and ash content following standard methods. Some characteristic properties of the sorbents are presented in Table 1. Scanning Electron Microscopy (LEICA S440) and FTIR spectroscopy (JASCO-FT/IR-460+) were also carried out on selected materials.

Measurement of fluoride :

Spectrophotometric method based on the reaction of fluoride with a zirconium dye lake was followed for the measurement of fluoride concentration in water¹⁸. Fluoride reacts with the dye dissociating proportional amount into a colorless complex [ZrF₆]²⁻, thus as the concentration of fluoride increases, the color (absorbance) progressively decreases.

Dilute standard solutions in the concentration range of 0.0–2.0 ppm F⁻ were prepared from a 20 ppm (20 µg/ml of F⁻) standard stock solution of fluoride (A.R. grade NaF). To 50 ml of each standard solution, 5 ml of sodium 2-parasulfophenylazo 1,8-dihydroxy 3,6-naphthalene disulphonate (SPADNS) reagent was added followed by 5 ml zirconyl acid reagent, mixed well and absorbance was measured at 570 nm with distilled water as reference. A concentration-absorbance reference calibration curve was plotted.

Batch tests for fluoride pick-up by RH silicarbons :

100 ml of F⁻ solution of known concentration (5–10 ppm F⁻) was shaken for a fixed duration with 1.0 g of silicarbon material in polypropylene bottle and was filtered. In 50 ml of filtrate SPADNS and zirconyl acid reagent were added exactly in the same way as used for the standards for measuring absorbance at 570 nm. For comparison, few other sorbents – RH itself, silicarbon derived from untreated RH, carbon derived from silicarbon (silica being leached out with warm 1 N NaOH) and a commercially active carbon from coconut shell – were also similarly tested.

Fluoride pick-up in a column with packed bed of iron-impregnated silicarbon :

A glass column (capacity vol 300 ml, id 2.5 cm) was set up with 10 g of Fe-impregnated silicarbon material (bed vol ~100 ml, bed length 15.1 cm) held between layers of gravel + coarse sand and fine sand at bottom and top respectively and plugged with glass wool at the ends.

The column bed was washed thoroughly by passing (downflow) distilled water through it and the system was checked for controlled steady outflow rates without channeling.

Aqueous solution of fluoride of known concentration (5.0 ppm F⁻) was passed through the column maintaining steady outflow rates of ~25 ml min⁻¹. Samples of 50 ml were collected at intervals for measuring residual F⁻ concentration in the effluents. The first sample was drawn after allowing 500 ml flowing out of the column.

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